

#1 ("Choledochal Cyst"[Mesh]) OR (((((((((((("Choledochal Cyst"[Title/Abstract]) OR ("Choledochal Cysts"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Choledochal Cysts"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Bile Duct Cyst"[Title/Abstract])) OR (Choledochoceles[Title/Abstract])) OR (Choledochoceles[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Choledochal Diverticulum"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Choledochal Diverticulum"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Congenital Biliary Dilatation"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Congenital Biliary Dilatations"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Common Bile Duct Choledochal Cyst"[Title/Abstract])) OR (("Caroli Disease"[Mesh]) OR (((((((("Caroli Disease"[Title/Abstract]) OR ("Caroli's Disease"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Carolis Disease"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Caroli's Syndrome"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Caroli Syndrome"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Carolis Syndrome"[Title/Abstract]))))

#2 ("Laparoscopy"[Mesh]) OR (((((((((((Laparoscopy[Title/Abstract]) OR (Laparoscopies[Title/Abstract])) OR (Celioscopy[Title/Abstract])) OR (Celioscopies[Title/Abstract])) OR (Peritoneoscopy[Title/Abstract])) OR (Peritoneoscopies[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Laparoscopic Surgical Procedures"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Laparoscopic Surgical Procedure"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Laparoscopic Surgery"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Laparoscopic Surgeries"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Laparoscopic Assisted Surgery"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Laparoscopic Assisted Surgeries"[Title/Abstract]))

#3 ("Robotic Surgical Procedures"[Mesh]) OR (((((((((((("Robotic Surgical Procedures"[Title/Abstract]) OR ("Robotic Surgical Procedure"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Robot Surgery"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Robot Surgeries"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Robot-Assisted Surgery"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Robot Assisted Surgery"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Robot-Assisted Surgeries"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Robot-Enhanced Procedures"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Robot Enhanced Procedures"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Robot-Enhanced Procedure"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Robotic-Assisted Surgery"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Robotic Assisted Surgery"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Robotic-Assisted Surgeries"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Robot-Enhanced Surgery"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Robot Enhanced Surgery"[Title/Abstract]))

#4 ("Biliary Tract Surgical Procedures"[Mesh]) OR (((((((((((("Biliary Tract Surgical Procedures"[Title/Abstract]) OR ("Biliary Tract Surgical Procedure"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Biliary Surgical Procedure"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Biliary Surgical Procedure"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Biliary Tract Surgery"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Bile Duct Operation"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Bile Duct Surgery"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Bile Tract Surgery"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Biliary Surgery"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Biliary Tract Operation"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Biliary Tract

Reoperation"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Bile Tract
Reconstruction"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Bile Duct
Reconstruction"[Title/Abstract]))
#5 ("Surgical Procedures, Operative"[Mesh]) OR (((("Operative
Procedures"[Title/Abstract]) OR ("Operative Procedure"[Title/Abstract]))
OR ("Surgical Procedures"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Surgical
Procedure"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("Ghost Surgery"[Title/Abstract]))
#6 #2 OR #3 OR #4 OR #5
#7 #1 AND #6